

Comparative study of *Allium sativum* (Garlic) and *Margosa Tree* (*Neem*) as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent in Diabetes mellitus type II

Dr. Deependra Sharma, * Dr. Meena Varma and **Dr. Prasanna Purohit

Asst. Prof. at GMERS Medical Collage, Valsad, Gujrat, *Department of Biochemistry, MGM Medical College and Associate Hospital, Indore and **Dr. A. P. J. Abdul Kalam University Indore M.P.

Abstract:

In the current study, 60 obese and diabetic subjects between the ages of 35 and 55 were examined to determine the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of garlic pods and Neem seed powder. Both serum lipids and serum glucose were measured for each individual. The current study's findings suggest that the use of herbs is safe and beneficial in the early stages of type 2 diabetes, with *garlic* (*allium sativum*) being the best hypoglycemic agent when compared to *margosa trees* (*neem*).

Keyword: Diabetes mellitus type II, *Alium sativum*, *Margosa Tree*, medicinal plants.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus, also known as "Madhumeha," has been well-known for centuries and has turned into a global disease. A disruption of glucose homeostasis characterizes this chronic metabolic disease. Diabetes is a chronic, untreatable illness that affects practically all of the body's organs and systems. Several plants have proven helpful for people with diabetes. Neem trees have many unique compounds that have been identified and others that are as yet unidentified, most analyzed compounds are-**Nimbin** (C₂₈H₄₀O₈) - Anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic, anti-histaminic, anti-fungal, **Nimbidin** – Anti – tuberculous, anti-protozoal, anti-pyretic, **Gendering**- Vasodilator, anti-malarial, anti-fungal, **Sodium Nimbinat** – Diuretic, spermicidal, anti-arthritic, **Quercetin** – anti-protozoal, **Salannin** – repellent and **Azadirachtin** – repellent, anti-feedant, anti-hormonal. (Siddiqui, 1945) & Santhoskumari, 1990, observed that Neem leaf tea significantly reduces the need for insulin. Neem leaf extract is a traditional herb for treating diabetes (Alam, et al., 1989) and has been scientifically proven effective in treating & preventing diabetes; (Murty, 1978); (Chakrabarty, 1984a). Oral doses of leaf extracts significantly reduced insulin requirements for non-insulin depended diabetes. (Pillai, 1981 b); (Luscombe, 1974); Murty

(1978). Aqueous extract of neem leaves significantly decreases blood sugar level and prevents adrenaline as well as glucose-induced hyperglycemia. (Murthy, K.S. et al 1978). A bud of Garlic inserted in ear also relieves pain. Garlic is also used in Paralysis, arthritis, sciatica and weak memory with good effect. Garlic juices are given internally in diminished vision. Garlic is also used in indigestion, low appetite, pain in abdomen, constipation, worm infestation. (Williamson, 2003) Allicin gives garlic its characteristics pungent smell Vitamins and mineral (Bravo, 2003; Gruenwald, 2004) (McCann, 2003) (Skidmore - Roth, 2003), Garlic purportedly lowers circulating triglycerides and cholesterol (Wichtl, 2004) garlic lowers down cholesterol and triglycerides in serum (Chetty et al., 2003) observed the decreasing trend lipids in a study.(McCrindle et al., 2002). Alliin, one of its sulfurs containing compounds, apparently has an inhibitory effect upon key enzymes involved in cholesterol biosynthesis, such as HMG Co a reductase (Schulz et al., 2004). A meta-analysis of selected clinical trials employing garlic preparations showed significant reduction on total serum cholesterol levels in human subjects (Warshafsky et al, 1993).

A Meta analysis of selected clinical trials employing garlic preparation showed significant reduction of total serum cholesterol, in human subjects Garlic purportedly lowers circulating triglycerides. It is one of those herbs which have favorable effect as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent. The main aim of this study was to see the effect of Garlic pods as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic in Diabetes melitus type 2.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD:

2.1 Experiment Place:

This study was conducted in Dept. of Biochemistry M.G.M. Medical College and Associated M.Y. Hospital Indore. And the subjects were selected from the outpatient Department of Medicine M Y Hospital Indore

2.2 Plant Collection:

All the plant components are bought from Ayurvedic shop Indore.

2.3 Inclusion Criteria:

Selection of subjects was done on basis of Blood Glucose not more than 180 mg/dl and HBA1C not more than 8mg%

2.4 Exclusion criteria:

History of any other clinical complication, taking any drug therapy Pregnant and lactating ladies.

Subjects were informed about the study in detail and consent was also taken before study.

2.5 Ethics Committee: The Ethics Committee of MGM Medical College approved the study.

2.6 Normal Healthy Control (n=50):

2.7 Study Subjects (n=200):

Estimations of the Biochemical parameters were done on study subjects then were compared with Healthy control.

2.8 Study subjects were divided into groups

i) Garlic group (n=40) &

ii) Neem Group (n=40)

2.9 Procedure:

A study was done to evaluate the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of garlic pods and Neem seed powder. Among the 60 obese and diabetic subject of 35 years to 55 years. 10 were taken as healthy control and 25 diabetic and obese were treated with garlic pods and 25 were treated with Neem seed powder. The criteria of inclusion of study group in subjects was FBS > 110 mg/dl of glucose, >290 mg/dl of cholesterol, > 210 mg/dl of triglyceride, than 180 mg/dl of LDL. All the subjects were examined for serum glucose and serum lipids. Garlic pods & Neem seed powder 100mgs/day was given to the subjects of study group for 6 months and sample were collected at the starting day of study after two months, fourth and after six months of study for estimation of all parameters

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table No.01. COMPARISION BETWEEN GARLIC AND NEEM SUPPLEMENT GROUPS AFTER A PERIOD OF TWO MONTH

PARAMETER	GARLIC Mean 2 Std. Deviation	NEEM Mean 2 Std. Deviation	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	127.80±16.95	131.20±9.36	0.80	>0.05
PPBG mg/dl	182.88±17.48	178.85±6.73	0.97	>0.05
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	251.68±25.42	256.80±10.48	0.84	>0.05

TG mg/dl	109.00±6.28	105.80±5.16	1.83	>0.05
HDL mg/dl	41.72±4.67	45.60±2.28	3.39	<0.001
LDL	68.88±14.32	60.90±3.43	2.43	<0.001
HBA1C	6.94±.33	7.33±.23	4.39	<0.001
UREA mg/dl	26.12±3.45	26.75±4.60	0.52	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.82±.100	.88±.093	1.99	>0.05
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.80±.37	3.96±.42	1.33	>0.05

After two months - Fasting blood Glucose, Post Prandial blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine and Serum Uric Acid are non-significant and there are similar decreases in the biochemical parameters for both these herbs. Serum HDL Cholesterol, Serum LDL Cholesterol and HbA1c are found to be significant after two months of supplementation

Table No. 02 COMPARISION BETWEEN GARLIC AND NEEM SUPPLEMENT GROUPS AFTER A PERIOD OF FOUR MONTH

PARAMETER	GARLIC Mean 4 Std. Deviation	NEEM Mean 4 Std. Deviation	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	109.88±16.45	108.25±11.47	0.37	>0.05
PPBG mg/dl	153.00±18.49	139.95±8.76	3.90	<0.0001
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	234.12±22.54	243.10±7.77	1.69	>0.05
TG mg/dl	108.04±5.43	101.60±2.72	4.82	<0.0001
HDL mg/dl	47.72±4.30	49.70±4.23	1.54	>0.05
LDL	67.80±12.79	54.05±4.34	4.58	<0.0001
HBA1C	6.340±.35	6.21±.41	1.09	>0.05
UREA mg/dl	25.12±3.89	24.35±3.42	0.70	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.818±.10	.85±.10	1.27	>0.05

URIC ACID mg/dl	3.96±.35	3.96±.45	0.079	>0.05
-----------------	----------	----------	-------	-------

After four months -Fasting blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum HDL Cholesterol, HbA1c, Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine, Serum Uric Acid are non-significant. Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Triglycerides and Serum LDL Cholesterol are found to be highly significant. The biochemical parameters after four months of oral supplementation of garlic were more effectively decreased than Neem

Table No. 03 COMPARISION BETWEEN GARLIC AND NEEM SUPPLEMENT GROUPS AFTER A PERIOD OF SIX MONTH

PARAMETER	GARLIC Mean 6 Std. Deviation	NEEM Mean 6 Std. Deviation	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	91.73±14.10	95.60±5.70	1.15	>0.05
PPBG mg/dl	140.50±16.59	139.70±9.09	0.19	>0.05
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	219.84±15.61	233.15±4.34	3.69	<0.001
TG mg/dl	109.46±5.44	100.35±4.97	5.83	<0.0001
HDL mg/dl	48.53±5.47	60.05±5.13	7.26	<0.0001
LDL	66.42±15.39	51.90±3.78	4.11	<0.0001
HBA1C	5.67±.39	5.87±.66	1.25	>0.05
UREA mg/dl	22.50±3.62	22.75±3.53	0.23	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.82±.094	.84±.08	0.9	>0.05
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.75±.43	3.73±.45	0.14	>0.05

After six months- Fasting blood Glucose, Post Prandial blood Glucose, HbA1c, Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine, Serum Uric Acid was found to be non-significant. Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum HDL Cholesterol, Serum LDL Cholesterol were highly significant. There were marked differences in these parameters after supplementation of both these herbs six months

4. CONCLUSION:

Results of the current research Conclude that Allium Sativum (garlic) is the best hypoglycemic agent in comparison to Margosa Tree (neem), and that herbal treatment is safe and efficient in the early stages of Diabetes mellitus type 2.

The herb *Allium Sativum* (garlic), which is a common choice for folk medicine and also has to be taken into consideration as a source for alternative medicine, is highlighted in the current studies as having the best hypoglycemic agent.

5. REFERENCES:

1. Stix G Village pharmacy. The neem tree yields products from pesticides to soap. *Sci Am.* 1992; 266:132.
2. Michael Tierra – Planetary Herbology (1942, Lotus Press). Neem Foundation.
3. Siddiqui, S. (1945) –*Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research.* 4:5-10.
4. Santhosh Umari, K.S., Deveji, K.S.– *Ancient science of life*, (1990) 9(4): 221-22.
5. Skula, R-Singh, S & Bhandari, CR. – *Medicine & Surgery* (1973) 13:11-12.
6. Murty, K.S. Rao, D.N., Rao, D.K. and Murthy, L.B.G. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology.* 1978 10: 247-250.
7. Chakraborty (1984a) *Prod. Nat. Symp. On Applied Biotech of Med. Aromatic Timber Yielding Plants.* 12-13 Jan, 1984 PP. 370-380.
8. Pillai, N.R. and Santhakumari, G. *Indian Journal of Medical Research* 1981 74:931-933.
9. Luscombe, (1974) *Journal of Pharmacy & Pharmacology.* 26: suppl. 111.
10. Williamson E. *Potter's Herbal Cyclopedia.* London: C.W. Daniel; 2003.
11. *Bravol. Farmacognosia.* Madrid: Elsevier Espana; 2003.
12. Gruenwald J. *PDR for Herbal Medicines* 3rd ed. Montvale, NJ: Thomson PDR; 2004.
13. McCann J. *Herbal Medicine Handbook* 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott; 2003.
14. Skidmore-Roth L. *Handbook of Herbs and Natural Supplements* 2 n ed. St. Louis: Mosby; 2003.
15. Chetty KN, Calahan L, Harris KC et al. Garlic attenuates hypercholesterolemic risk factors hi olive oil fed rats and high cholesterol fed rats. *Pathophysiology.* 2003;9(3): 127-132.
16. McCrindle BW, Helden E, Conner WT. Garlic extract therapy in children with hypercholesterolemia. *Ar Pediatr Adolesc Med*;152(11):1089-94.,2002.
17. Warshafsky S, Kamer RS, Sivak SL. Effect of garlic on total serum cholesterol. A meta-analysis. *Ann Intern Med.* 1993 Oct 1;119(7 Pt 1):599-605. Doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-119-7_part_1-199310010-00009. PMID: 8363171.